

Titrimetric Microdetermination of some Sulphur-containing Amino Acids

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MICRODETERMINATION of sulphur-containing amino acids has been reviewed by Cheronis and Ma¹ and Ashworth². Glutathione reduced (GSH) is determined either by oxidimetric methods or by those involving mercaptide formation. The oxidimetric methods require strict adherence to the specified reaction conditions in order to accomplish stoichiometric reaction. Silver(I) and mercury(II) have been extensively used in the latter group of methods. Both direct and indirect titrimetric procedures have been suggested, but for microdetermination, electrometric titration methods³⁻⁵ are recommended. Forbes and Hamlin⁷ have used organomercuric reagents for determining GSH by visual or amperometric titration method.

On treating a solution of GSH with an excess of mercuric chloride, an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid is produced which can be titrated with standard alkali and thus the amount of GSH present in the test solution can be computed. But this titration is difficult and inaccurate because of the appearance of the yellow precipitate of mercuric hydroxide prior to the equivalence point. In the proposed method, this difficulty has been circumvented by adding an excess of potassium iodide before titrating the liberated acid. The iodide forms a stable soluble complex with residual mercuric chloride, thereby rendering the use of phenolphthalein indicator possible.

The determination of cystine involves either its reduction to cysteine which is then determined or its oxidation to S(IV) or S(VI) stages using *N*-bromosuccinimide⁶, iodosocompounds⁸, bromine chloride¹⁰, chloramine-T¹¹ etc. With bromine chloride, the stoichiometry depends critically on reaction conditions, whereas the quantitative oxidation with phenyliodoacetate involves long reaction periods. The proposed oxidimetric micromethod for determining GSH, cystine and methionine consists of titrating the sample solution with a standard potassium iodate solution in 4–6 *M* hydrochloric acid medium in presence of carbon tetrachloride¹².

Experimental

The following solutions were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals and conductivity water.

A 0.1 *M* sodium hydroxide solution standardised with oxalic acid, was diluted to obtain 0.05, 0.025 and 0.0125 *M* solutions. A 0.025 *M* potassium iodate solution was diluted to get 0.01, 0.005 and 0.0025 *M* solutions. A saturated solution of

mercuric chloride in water and 1% phenolphthalein solution in 1:1 ethanol–water mixture was prepared. Solutions of amino acids (0.025 *M*) were prepared and standardised by the methods indicated in Table 2.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF GSH WITH MERCURIC CHLORIDE

Taken*	GSH (mg)		Relative standard deviation %
	Found**		
76.84	76.99		0.15
38.42	38.56		0.20
19.21	19.26		0.30

* Average of 6 determinations. ** Standardised by iodometry.

TABLE 2—MICRODETERMINATION OF GSH, METHIONINE AND CYSTINE WITH POTASSIUM IODATE

Compd.	Amount (mg)		Relative standard deviation %	Number of equivalents consumed per mole
	Comparison method	Proposed method*		
GSH	30.74 ^a	30.82	0.30	6
	15.37	15.42	0.33	
	7.69	7.72	0.40	
Methionine	29.84 ^b	29.87	0.11	4
	14.92	14.94	0.28	
	3.74	3.75	0.30	
Cystine**	24.03 ^c	24.09	0.23	10
	12.02	12.05	0.25	
	3.00	3.02	0.20	

* Average of six determinations. ** Solution prepared in 1 *M* HCl. ^aIodimetry. ^bChloramine-T¹¹. ^c*N*-Bromosuccinimide⁶.

Procedure :

Determination of GSH with mercuric chloride : An aliquot (5–10 ml) of the test solution containing GSH (0.05–0.2 mmol) was taken in a 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask, treated with a saturated solution of mercuric chloride (3 ml) and the flask swirled for 1–2 min. Solid potassium iodide (1–2 g) was then gradually added with shaking until the red precipitate of mercuric iodide, first formed, dissolved. Phenolphthalein indicator solution (5 drops) was then added and the contents titrated with a standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Determination of GSH, cystine and methionine by titration with potassium iodate : An aliquot of the test solution (5–10 ml containing 0.02–0.1 mmol of the substance) was taken in a 250 ml iodine flask, concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 ml) and carbon tetrachloride (5 ml) were added. A standard potassium iodate solution was then gradually added through a burette with constant shaking until the aqueous layer became pale brown. The flask was then stoppered and vigorously shaken when the carbon tetrachloride layer acquired a purple tinge due to iodine. Dropwise addition of the iodate titrant with constant shaking was continued until the organic layer lost the last tinge of violet leaving only pale yellow colour due to iodine monochloride.

Results and Discussion

The proposed method for determining GSH with mercuric chloride is rapid, simple and accurate. The reaction conditions are not critical and accurate results are readily obtained even with microsamples. It is not necessary to prepare an organomercuric derivative which has to be used in certain other procedures⁷.

The advantage of the method is that the addition of potassium iodide to bind the unreacted Hg^{II} permits the use of phenolphthalein indicator. Indicators like methyl orange and methyl red which show a colour change on the acid side of the equivalence point, do not give satisfactory results. But these had to be used by previous workers^{13,14} in order to avoid interference due to the formation of a yellow precipitate of mercuric hydroxide formed prior to the end-point if indicators like phenolphthalein are used. Out of the two carboxyl groups present on two different carbon atoms in GSH, one is neutralised by the presence of amino group on the same carbon atom containing the carboxyl group, while the other is titrated along with the acid liberated in the course of the reaction with mercuric chloride. Each molecule of GSH hence corresponds to two equivalents of alkali; thus permitting determination of GSH at micro level. It may be noted that although amperometric procedure with silver nitrate is quite sensitive, the reaction mixture should be protected from aerial oxidation. Furthermore, neighbouring amino and carboxyl groups may cause positive error.

The oxidimetric determination of GSH, cystine and methionine involves titration with potassium iodate in 4–5 M hydrochloric acid medium when iodate is reduced to I⁺ ion. The equivalent weight of potassium iodate in these titrations is one-fourth of its molecular weight as against one-sixth in cases using low acidity¹⁵. The end-point is quite sharp even with 0.0025 M potassium iodate as the titrant.

The number of equivalents consumed per gm-mole of reductant (Table 2) show that in GSH and cystine, the oxidation results in the formation of sulphonic acids whereas in the case of methionine the product is a sulphone.

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A Rapid Oxidimetric Determination of Psychotropic Drugs with Cerium(IV)†

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MEPAZINE hydrochloride (MH), perazine dimalonate (PDM) and propionyl promazine phosphate (PPP) belong to phenothiazine class of drugs, which are widely used for the treatment of patients with emotional or mental disorders.

A number of methods^{1–6} are known for the assay of phenothiazines but they are either time consuming or reagents used are not always readily available. Farkas and Kraaznai⁷, Blazek⁸, and Agrawal and Blake⁹ have determined phenothiazines by oxidation with cerium(IV). A comprehensive survey of the literature revealed that no attempt was made for the determination of MH, PDM and PPP. The present paper describes the oxidimetric determination of these drugs with cerium(IV).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade unless otherwise stated. Stock solutions of MH, PDM and PPP were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of the sample in water, standardised gravimetrically¹ and stored in a refrigerator. A 0.05 N cerium(IV) sulphate was prepared in 2N sulphuric acid and standardised titrimetrically¹⁰.

Procedures :

Determination of MH, PDM or PPP : An aliquot of the stock solution (containing up to 180 mg of MH or 300 mg of PPP) was diluted to 40 ml, 5N sulphuric acid (10 ml) was added and the mixture was titrated with 0.05 N cerium(IV) sulphate. In the

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